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Increased hypothalamic serotonin turnover in inflammation-induced anorexia

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Abstract

Background: Anorexia can occur as a serious complication of disease. Increasing evidence suggests that inflammation plays a major role, along with a hypothalamic dysregulation characterized by locally elevated serotonin levels. The present study was undertaken to further explore the connections between peripheral inflammation, anorexia and hypothalamic serotonin metabolism and signaling pathways. First, we investigated the response of two hypothalamic neuronal cell lines to TNF α , IL-6 and LPS. Next, we studied transcriptomic changes and serotonergic activity in the hypothalamus of mice after intraperitoneal injection with TNF α , IL-6 or a combination of TNF α and IL-6.

Results: In vitro, we showed that hypothalamic neurons responded to inflammatory mediators by releasing cytokines. This inflammatory response was associated with an increased serotonin release. Mice injected with TNF α and IL-6 showed decreased food intake, associated with altered expression of inflammation-related genes in the hypothalamus. In addition, hypothalamic serotonin turnover showed to be elevated in treated mice.

Conclusions: Overall, our results underline that peripheral inflammation reaches the hypothalamus where it affects hypothalamic serotonergic metabolism. These hypothalamic changes in serotonin pathways are associated with decreased food intake, providing evidence for a role of serotonin in inflammation-induced anorexia.

Background

Loss of appetite (anorexia) leading to insufficient food intake is often seen in chronic illnesses including cancer, HIV and COPD. A chronically elevated increased inflammatory tone is considered one of the major drivers of anorexia in these diseases. Studies suggest that an ongoing elevated inflammatory tone in the hypothalamus, displaying the highest density of various cytokine receptors in the brain [1], is implicated in these disturbances in food intake. Inflammatory mediators affect important orexigenic and anorexigenic regulators including NPY [2] and POMC [3, 4] peptides in the hypothalamus. Cytokines and other pro-inflammatory signalling molecules from the periphery are able to reach the hypothalamus passing the blood brain barrier (BBB) [5–7]. In addition, de novo synthesis of various cytokines in the hypothalamus has been reported [8]. To trigger these

processes, sensing of peripheral signals in the adjacent median eminence [9, 10] and activation of hypothalamic microglial and astrocyte cells [11, 12] might be crucial.

We previously described changes in hypothalamic serotonin signalling in rodent tumour models displaying severe body wasting (cachexia). These changes in serotonin formation were inversely associated with food intake [13]. This is in line with findings in a variety of chronic illnesses, where increased hypothalamic serotonin has been implicated for its role in the development of disease-associated anorexia [14–17]. Hypothalamic serotonin plays an important role in food intake, since it is able to respond to peripheral signals on energy status [18–20] and it is able to modulate anorexigenic and orexigenic signalling in the hypothalamus. Serotonin is able to affect food intake via activation of the anorexigenic melanocortin system involving 5HT_{2c} receptors [21] and by inhibition of the orexigenic NPYergic system [15, 22]. Furthermore, reduction of brain serotonin by reducing availability of its precursor tryptophan (TRP) (Fig. 1) has been shown to be beneficial in the treatment in anorexia during cancer [23].

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In the present study, we investigated the anorexigenic effects of TNF α and IL-6, cytokines that are often elevated during chronic illness, on hypothalamic serotonin signalling. To test physiologically relevant concentrations of TNF α and IL-6 in illness, we included two combinations containing both TNF α and IL-6 that reflected plasma levels measured in C26 adenocarcinoma tumour-bearing mice or Lewis Lung tumour-bearing mice respectively [13, 24]. We show that these cytokines when administered intraperitoneally (ip) induce changes in the hypothalamic transcriptome consistent with changes in inflammatory pathways and serotonin signalling. Furthermore, these cytokines alter hypothalamic levels of serotonin's main metabolite 5-HIAA (Fig. 1), indicating that synaptic serotonin release [25, 26] and serotonin turnover [27, 28] is affected by inflammation.

Results

IL-6, TNF α and LPS increase inflammatory markers, 5HT and 5-HIAA in hypothalamic cell lines

Exposure of hypothalamic cell lines hypoE-46 and hypoA2/12 to IL-6 (100 pg/ml), TNF α (100 pg/ml) and LPS (1 μ g/ml) for 24 h stimulated serotonin (5HT) release into the medium. Furthermore, levels of intracellular

5-hydroxyindoleacetic acid (5-HIAA) were elevated after exposure to IL-6, TNF α and LPS in both cell lines. Both cell lines produced IL-6 when exposed to IL-6, since levels detected were four to sixfold higher than exposed levels. In addition, both cell lines produced MCP-1 when exposed to LPS and IL-6. Compared to IL-6 and LPS, TNF α showed to be less potent in inducing the production of MCP-1 and IL-6 (Fig. 2). No TNF α release was detected (data not shown) after exposure to IL-6, TNF α or LPS.

IL-6 and TNF α reduce food intake in mice

Hourly food intake remained constant in control animals during the entire study period. In cytokine treated mice, food intake curves started to deviate from 2 h after injection, becoming significantly lower 4 h after injection in the TNF α , IL-6 high, IL-6 Low + TNF α and IL-6 High + TNF α groups, compared to controls (Fig. 3). These effects did not differ between cytokine treatments. After 5 h of injection, food intake between all groups was similar again.

Plasma levels of cytokines and serum amyloid A levels in liver were measured 5 h after injection. There were three groups with significant changes in plasma TNF α ,

IL-6 or liver SAA levels: the two combination groups and the IL-6 high group. Plasma IL-6 was significantly higher in the two combination groups, while TNF α was increased in the IL-6 high and the TNF + IL-6 Low group. The elevation of the other combination group did not reach significance. Liver SAA was only significantly increased in the IL-6 high group (Fig. 3). Plasma levels of MCP-1, leptin, resistin, PYY, amylin, GIP, GLP-1 and insulin were not different between groups (Additional file 1: Figure 1). Ghrelin, pancreatic peptide and glucagon plasma levels were below detection limit of the assay.

IL-6 and TNF α increase hypothalamic 5-HIAA and TRP

Total hypothalamic serotonin (5HT) tissue concentrations were not affected by injection with TNF and/or IL-6 5 h after injection. However, serotonin's metabolite, 5-hydroxyindoleacetic acid (5HIAA), showed to be significantly elevated in hypothalamus homogenates of both the TNF + IL-6 Low and TNF + IL-6 High groups compared to controls (Fig. 4). These increases were more prominent than those following injection with TNF, IL-6 Low and IL-6 High alone. Tryptophan (TRP) showed to

be significantly higher in mice injected with TNF + IL-6 High compared to controls. Hypothalamic levels of dopamine (DA) and its metabolite 3,4-dihydroxyphenylacetic acid (DOPAC) showed no differences between groups (Fig. 4).

Hypothalamic transcriptome analysis: IL-6 and TNF α have similar effects on serotonin signalling and inflammatory pathways

Expression of genes that were changed with a fold change greater than 1.5 compared to controls were compared among the different groups, resulting in a list of 118 genes (Figs. 5, 6, 7). From these genes, 87 genes showed to be altered in a similar direction (either up or down compared to controls) in at least 4 out of 5 treatment groups. Furthermore, 96 out of 118 genes were overlapping between animals from the TNF and IL-6 Low or IL-6 High groups. Altogether this shows that induced changes on gene expression were overall similar for treatment with TNF, IL-6 or the combination. More importantly, gene expression of rate-limiting enzymes involved in the synthesis of 5HT, including *Tph2* and expression

Fig. 3 Effect of injection with TNF α , IL-6 or both on food intake and plasma cytokines. **a** Time course of food intake after injection with TNF α , IL-6 or both. **b, c** IL-6 and TNF α plasma levels 5 h after injection. **d** Level of serum amyloid 1 (SAA) in liver homogenates 5 h after injection. ^aSignificantly different from Control group ($P < 0.05$). Data is expressed as mean \pm SEM ($n = 12$)

of the serotonin-reuptake transporter, *Slc6a4*, were found to be among these highly upregulated genes. Strongly down-regulated genes included those of two important orexigenic regulators NPY and AgRP. Treatment effects showed to be similar for NPY and AgRP and these were most prominent in the IL-6 Low and TNF α + IL-6 Low groups (Figs. 5, 6, 7). Using Ingenuity, upstream regulators that were present in at least 3 treatment groups were listed (Table 1). Overall, this revealed an inflammatory profile of upstream regulators, which included cytokines IFN γ , TGF β and IL-6 and the enzyme I κ BKG which is an encoded protein of the I κ B complex, and crucial for activating NF κ B. The Ingenuity database used included 75 IFN γ target genes of which 19 out of 27 had an overlap with IL-6 target genes, which might explain the mutual presence of both these cytokines.

Discussion

Decreased food intake (anorexia) often occurs during conditions characterized by an elevated inflammatory response. In this study we investigated the role of serotonin in this decreased food intake during inflammation. Here, we show that both in vitro and in vivo hypothalamic inflammation is associated with increased serotonergic activity. Overall supporting the viewpoint that changes in hypothalamic 5HT signaling are involved in anorexia resulting from inflammation.

Interestingly, we found that the two hypothalamic cell lines used here (HypoE-46 and HypoA-2/12), which are derived from different neuronal populations of the hypothalamus, the PVN [29] and the ARC [30] respectively, are able to produce inflammatory mediators when exposed to LPS, TNF α or IL-6. Upon exposure to IL-6 and TNF α , neurons responded by the production of IL-6 and MCP-1, but not TNF α . MCP-1 production is regulated by IL-6, suggesting that MCP-1 production upon exposure to TNF might also involve the production of IL-6 [31].

So far, studies on hypothalamic inflammation have primarily focussed on the role of microglial and astrocyte activation [11, 12, 32, 33]. However, it has been shown

Fig. 4 Levels of tryptophan, serotonin and dopamine and their metabolites in the hypothalamus. Effect of ip injection with TNF α , IL-6 or both on **a** 5-hydroxyindoleacetic acid (5HIAA), **b** Serotonin (5HT), **c** 3,4-dihydroxyphenylacetic acid (DOPAC), **d** Dopamine (DA) and **e** tryptophan (TRP). ^aSignificantly different from Control group ($P < 0.05$), ^bsignificantly different from TNF, IL-6 Low and IL-6 High group ($P < 0.05$). Data is expressed as mean \pm SEM ($n = 6$)

(See figure on next page.)

Fig. 5 Gene expression changes in hypothalamus after ip injection with TNF α , IL-6 or both. Top upregulated genes and top downregulated genes in treated groups compared to control group. Each row represents a gene and each column represents a group of animals. Magenta colour indicates genes that were higher expressed as control and green colour indicates genes that were lower expressed as the control. Black indicates genes whose expression was similar to compared to control. ID: Entrez ID

Gene	TNF	IL-6 L	IL-6 H	TNF+IL-6 L	TNF+IL-6 H	ID	
Gh						14599	growth hormone
Gm8894						667952	myosin light polypeptide 6 a
Traj54						100124333	T cell receptor alpha 54
Vmn2r69						330581	vomeronal 2, receptor 69
Usp17ld						384701	ubiquitin specific peptidase 17
Gm3642						100042054	predicted gene 3642
Slc6a3						13162	solute carrier family 6 member 3
Prl						19109	prolactin
Vmn2r84						625068	vomeronal 2, receptor 84
Gm10651						100043771	predicted pseudogene 10651
Traj57						100124295	T cell receptor alpha joining 57
Slc10a4						231290	solute carrier family 10member 4
Chrna6						11440	cholinergic receptor 6
Olfr166						259071	olfactory receptor 166
Meis2						17536	Meis homeobox 2
Esp4						100126777	exocrine gland secreted peptide 4
Hapln1						12950	hyaluronan and proteoglycan 1
Nexn						68810	nexilin
Gm4130						100042959	predicted gene 4130
Lcn2						16819	lipocalin 2
Sema3e						20349	sema domain immunoglobulin 3E
Neurod1						18012	neurogenic differentiation 1
Chrn3						108043	cholinergic receptor polypeptide 3
H2-Q7						15018	histocompatibility 2, Q region locus 7
Ano3						228432	anoctamin 3
Cabp1						29867	calcium binding protein 1
Mctp2						244049	multiple C2 domainse 2
Dao						13142	D-amino acid oxidase
Vav3						57257	vav 3 oncogene
Ephx4						384214	epoxide hydrolase 4
Epcam						17075	epithelial cell adhesion molecule
Slc17a7						72961	solute carrier family 17 member 7
Snora41						100217464	small nucleolar RNA, H/ACA box 41
AW822252						331578	expressed sequence AW822252
Pou1f1						18736	POU domain transcription factor 1
Gabra6						14399	gamma-aminobutyric acid A 6
Mrto4						69902	MRT4 mRNA turnover 4
Tph2						216343	tryptophan hydroxylase 2
Cbln3						56410	cerebellin 3 precursor protein
Slc6a4						15567	solute carrier family 6 member 4
Vmn2r14						231591	vomeronal 2, receptor 14
Slc6a5						104245	solute carrier family 6 member 5
Lhx9						16876	LIM homeobox protein 9
Mir204						387200	microRNA 204
Mab2111						17116	mab-21-like 1
Hbb-b1						15129	hemoglobin beta adult major
Fshb						14308	follicle stimulating hormone beta
Pvalb						19293	parvalbumin
Ugt1a2						22236	UDP glucuronosyltransferase 1 A2
En2						13799	engrailed 2
Trdv4						100114901	T cell receptor delta variable 4
Cnpy1						269637	canopy 1 homolog
Fat2						245827	FAT tumor suppressor homolog 2
Mir9-2						723967	microRNA 9-2
Igll1						404737	immunoglobulin lambda joining 1
Lhb						16866	luteinizing hormone beta
Pomc						18976	pro-opiomelanocortin-alpha
Oacyl						319888	O-acyltransferase like
Abhd12b						100504285	abhydrolase domain containing 12B
Slitrk6						239250	SLIT and NTRK-like family, member 6
Synpo2						118449	synaptopodin 2
Olfr457						258989	olfactory receptor 457

Gene	TNF	IL-6 L	IL-6 H	TNF+IL-6 L	TNF+IL-6 H	ID	
Gm10439						382243	predicted gene 10439
Kcnj13						100040591	potassium channel member 13
Fmod						14264	fibromodulin
Slc13a4						243755	solute carrier family 13 member 4
Slc6a20a						102680	solute carrier family 6 member 20A
Osr1						23967	odd-skipped related 1
Aldh1a2						19378	aldehyde dehydrogenase family 1 A2
Prg4						96875	proteoglycan 4
Acta2						11475	actinalpha 2
Slc22a6						18399	solute carrier family 22 member 6
Slc6a13						14412	solute carrier family 6 member 13
Cyt11						231162	cytokine-like 1
Prlc5						107849	prolactin family 2, subfamily c, member 5
Emp3						13732	epithelial membrane protein 3
Ogn						18295	osteoglycin
Csf2rb2						12984	colony stimulating factor 2 receptor
H3f3a						15078	H3 histone, family 3A
Olf1354						259163	olfactory receptor 1354
Igfbp2						16008	insulin-like growth factor binding protein 2
Igf2						16002	insulin-like growth factor 2
Gpr182						11536	G protein-coupled receptor 182
Myl9						98932	myosin, light polypeptide 9, regulatory
Serping1						12258	serine peptidase inhibitor member 1
Ssxb1						67985	synovial sarcoma breakpoint 1
Itih2						16425	inter-alpha trypsin inhibitor heavy chain 2
Slc22a8						19879	solute carrier family 22 member 8
AgRP						11604	agouti related protein
Olf1162						258105	olfactory receptor 1162
H2-Aa						14960	histocompatibility 2, class II antigen A
Olf1362						258739	olfactory receptor 1362
Vtn						22370	vitronectin
Efemp1						216616	epidermal growth factor 1
Gm11710						100043123	predicted gene 11710
Ighv1-63						780956	immunoglobulin heavy variable V1-63
Gm13931						668825	predicted gene 13931
Snord37						100217454	small nucleolar RNA, C/D box 37
Gemin6						67242	gem associated protein 6
Ranbp3l						223332	RAN binding protein 3-like
3110039M2						67293	RIKEN cDNA 3110039M20 gene
Dcn						13179	decorin
Npy						109648	neuropeptide Y
Mpzl2						14012	myelin protein zero-like 2
Pin4						69713	protein NIMA-interacting 4
Car13						71934	carbonic anhydrase 13
Snora20						100303746	small nucleolar RNA, H/ACA box 20
Snord49a						100217455	small nucleolar RNA, C/D box 49A
Gm8096						666422	3-phosphoglycerate dehydrogenase
Bpifb9a						71425	BPI fold containing family B, member 9A
Trav12-1						630086	T cell receptor alpha variable 12-1
Cpt1b						12895	carnitine palmitoyltransferase 1b
Igkv10-94						667550	immunoglobulin kappa variable 10-94
Gm13202						433806	predicted gene 13202
Apol9a						223672	apolipoprotein L 9a
Olf403						404316	olfactory receptor 403
Tc2n						74413	tandem C2 domains, nuclear
Cga						12640	glycoprotein hormones, alpha subunit

(see figure on previous page.)

Fig. 6 Gene expression changes in hypothalamus after ip injection with TNF α , IL-6 or both. Top upregulated genes and top downregulated genes in treated groups compared to control group. Each row represents a gene and each column represents a group of animals. Magenta colour indicates genes that were higher expressed as control and green colour indicates genes that were lower expressed as the control. Black indicates genes whose expression was similar to compared to control. ID: Entrez ID

before that neurons also express high levels of various cytokines [34] and that synthesis of cytokines occurs in response to blood-borne inflammatory mediators [35]. This suggests that neurons may play a significant role in development and sustainment of hypothalamic inflammation. Furthermore, we showed that this inflammatory response in hypothalamic neurons coincided with elevated serotonin secretion and increased intracellular 5-HIAA levels, reflecting an increase in serotonin

turnover. In the mice, injection with combinations of TNF α and IL-6 resulted in increased hypothalamic 5-HIAA levels, while tissue serotonin levels did not differ from controls. A possible explanation for this apparent difference could be that in cell experiments, secreted serotonin was measured. However, in total tissue homogenates, intracellular serotonin cannot be distinguished from serotonin released into the synaptic cleft. Therefore, total tissue homogenate levels of serotonin do not

Table 1 Upstream regulators in hypothalamus after ip injection with TNF α and IL-6

Upstream regulators	TNF	IL-6 low	IL-6 high	TNF + IL-6 low	TNF + IL-6 high
Cytokines			IFNG	IFNG	
	IFNG	IFNG	IL6	IL6	
	IL6	IL6	PRL	PRL	IFNG
	TGFB1	PRL	TGFB1	TGFB1	TGFB1
Enzymes			TGFBR1	TGFBR1	
		TGFBR1	IKBKG	IKBKG	
	TGFBR1	IKBKG	ALDH1A2	ALDH1A2	
	ALDH1A2	PARP9	PARP9	PARP9	TGFB1
Transcription factors			SRF		
			MKL1	SRF	
	SRF		SMAD7	MKL1	
	MKL1	SMAD7	CEBPB	CEBPB	SRF
	STAT1	CEBPB	STAT1	STAT1	MKL1
	IRF3	IRF3	IRF3	IRF3	SMAD7

properly reflect its release, which has also been reported for other monoamines and catecholamines [36]. However, 5-HIAA, the stable metabolic end product of 5HT is considered to be a good reflection for serotonin release [37–39] and therefore widely acknowledged as marker for serotonergic activity [25, 26].

Levels of 5-HIAA are measured in different matrices, models and diseases, including various forms of depression and aggressive behaviour disorders, where measurement of 5-HIAA gives better results than that of serotonin. Alterations on 5-HIAA are more pronounced and long-lasting, while changes on serotonin can be rapidly diminished [27, 40–42].

In the current experimental setting, 5 HT and metabolites were measured 5 h after cytokine injection and it could be that alterations of serotonin levels had already diminished by then. A similar reasoning might explain why elevated levels of serotonin's precursor, tryptophan (TRP), were only prominent in mice injected with the combination of the highest dose of IL-6 and TNF α . Tryptophan levels have been reported to rise upon injection with cytokines depending on the type of inflammatory stimulus used. However at the same time, this inflammatory response is associated with increased TRP breakdown by indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase (IDO), to synthesize kynurenine [43, 44].

In plasma, levels of TNF α and IL-6 were not elevated in the groups treated with a single cytokine. However, when these cytokines were given in combination, high levels of IL-6 and TNF α were measured. It is likely that clearance of the administered cytokines already occurred within 5 h following injection. For both TNF α and IL-6, complete clearance from the circulation has been reported to occur within 6 h after ip injection [45, 46]. Furthermore levels of these cytokines have different temporal profiles, with TNF α plasma being fast responsive and also more rapidly cleared than IL-6 from the blood, but at the same time being more persistent in hypothalamus than IL-6 [47, 48].

Food intake showed to decrease in all treated groups and there was no difference between the treatments. It appears that the lowest dose of IL-6 was sufficient to induce an anorexigenic effect and that higher doses produced no additional anorexigenic activity. This is in line with other reports showing that in contrast to other IL-6 effects, there is no clear dose-dependency of IL-6 when it comes to its activity on food-intake [49, 50].

Whole genome gene expression profiles from the hypothalamus and the predicted inflammatory transcriptional regulators showed a high overlap between TNF α , IL-6 and combination groups, indicating that responses of the different treatments were similar. This might be explained by a production of similar cytokines by the

host in response to injection with IL-6 or TNF α . In hypothalamic tissue homogenates, increased levels of IL-6 have been reported after injection with TNF α [51], which suggests that injection with TNF α also leads to activation of IL-6 signalling pathways. The strong down-regulation of expression of two important orexigenic neuropeptide regulators NPY and AgRP also showed to be similar between groups and corresponded to lower food intake in treated groups. This decrease in expression induced by TNF α or IL-6 supports findings that have been reported in a variety of experimental models including hypothalamic injection with TNF α and genetic overexpression of hypothalamic IL-6 [52, 53].

Gene expression of two genes involved in serotonin signalling, showed to be upregulated in mice treated with TNF α and IL-6. Serotonin has been reported to have an inhibiting action on NPY [13, 54, 55], suggesting that the increase in serotonergic activity measured in treated mice, might be responsible for the effects on lower NPY expression in these mice.

Conclusions

In summary, we show that TNF α and IL-6 induce similar inflammatory responses in the hypothalamus and similar effects on food intake. This anorexigenic effect of TNF α and IL-6 showed to coincide with increased hypothalamic serotonergic activity, providing further evidence for a role for serotonin in inflammation-induced anorexia.

Methods

Cell culture and in vitro studies with IL-6, TNF α and LPS

Murine derived hypothalamic neuronal cell lines hypoE-46 and hypoA2/12 (CELLutions Biosystems Inc. Canada) were grown and maintained in DMEM supplemented with 10 % heat-inactivated fetal calf serum, 100 U/ml penicillin and 100 μ g/ml streptomycin at 37 °C under 5.0 % CO₂. Cells were grown in monolayers to 90 % confluency. Then medium was replaced by serum-free DMEM containing penicillin and streptomycin. After 4 h, cells were exposed to LPS (1 μ g/ml), TNF α (100 pg/ml), IL-6 (100 pg/ml) for 24 h, or KCl (60 mM) for 15 min. After exposure, supernatant was collected to measure levels of serotonin (BAE-5900, LDN, Nordhorn, Germany), IL-6 (DY406, Abingdon, UK), TNF α (DY410, Abingdon, UK) and MCP-1 (DY479, R&D systems, Abingdon, UK) by enzyme-immuno assay. Cells were homogenized in 40 mM Tris, 1 mM EDTA, 5 mM EGTA and 0.50 % Triton X-100. Homogenates were used to measure 5-hydroxyindoleacetic acid (5-HIAA) by ELISA (MBS261481, MyBiosource, Breda, The Netherlands) and corrected for total protein content (Pierce Bicinchoninic acid Rockford, IL, USA). Cytotoxicity was determined by measuring LDH leakage and cell viability using an XTT

conversion assay after 48 h of exposure (Roche Diagnostics, Mannheim, Germany). All experiments were performed three times in quadruplicate.

Animals

C57BL/6 male mice (Harlan, Horst, The Netherlands), weighing approximately 20 g, were individually housed 1 week before start of the experiment. Mice were maintained on a 12 h light:12 h dark cycle in a climate-controlled room (21 ± 1 °C). Standard diet was ad libitum available during the entire experiment from one hour prior to dark phase until start of the light phase (Arie Blok B.V., Woerden, and The Netherlands). Water was freely available 24 h a day. Food intake, water intake and body weight were monitored daily from 1 week prior to the end of the experiment.

All experimental procedures were made in accordance with the European Community guidelines for the use of laboratory animals and complied with the principles of good laboratory animal care.

Experimental set-up

Mice were injected intraperitoneal (ip) with 50 μ l of saline vehicle (G-Biosciences, St. Louis, USA), TNF α (Peprotech, London, UK), IL-6 (Peprotech, London, UK), or both TNF α and IL-6. The study included 6 groups: Control, TNF α , IL-6 Low, IL-6 High, TNF α + IL-6 Low and TNF α + IL-6 High (Table 2). The rationale to study different doses and combinations of IL-6 was based on our previous observations in mouse tumour models and the generally recognized central role of IL-6 as link between cancer and inflammation [13, 24]. Combinations TNF + IL-6 Low and TNF + IL-6 High reflect plasma levels measured in C26 tumour-bearing mice and Lewis Lung tumour-bearing mice respectively. Each group included 12 mice, of which 6 mice were used for determination of hypothalamic metabolites and 6 mice were used for hypothalamic gene expression analysis. Mice were injected 1 h prior to the dark phase. Five hours after injection, blood was collected by cardiac puncture under general anaesthesia. After sacrifice, brain, hypothalamus and organs were weighted, frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80 °C.

Table 2 Experimental groups

Group	Nr of mice	Treatment (IP injection 50 μ l sodium chloride)
Control	12	Sodium chloride 0.9 %
TNF	12	15 pg TNF α
IL-6 low	12	50 pg IL-6
IL-6 high	12	800 pg IL-6
TNF + IL-6 low	12	50 pg IL-6 + 15 pg TNF α
TNF + IL-6 high	12	800 pg IL-6 + 15 pg TNF α

Hypothalamic metabolites 5-HT, 5-HIAA, DA, DOPAC and TRP

Hypothalamus tissue was homogenised by sonication in 10 μ l of 0.5 M perchloric acid per mg of tissue and stored at -80 °C until analysis. Concentrations of DA, 5-HT, DOPAC, 5-HIAA and TRP were determined by HPLC with tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS) detection, using deuterated internal standards of the analytes. Of each LC-MS sample, an aliquot was injected onto the HPLC column by an automated sample injector (SIL10-20AC-HT, Shimadzu, Japan). Chromatographic separation was performed on a SynergiMax column (100 \times 3.0 mm, particle size 3 μ m) held at a temperature of 35 °C. The mobile phases consisted of A: ultrapurified H₂O + 0.1 % formic and B: acetonitrile: ultrapurified H₂O (75:25) + 0.1 % formic acid. Elution of the compounds proceeded using a suitable linear gradient at a flow rate of 0.3 ml/min. The MS analyses were performed using an API 4000 MS/MS system consisting of an API 4000 MS/MS detector and a Turbo Ion Spray interface (Applied Biosystems, the Netherlands). The acquisitions on API 4000 were performed in positive ionization mode for 5-HT, DA and TRP and in negative mode for 5-HIAA and DOPAC, with optimized settings for the analytes. The instrument was operated in multiple-reaction-monitoring (MRM) mode.

Data were calibrated and quantified using the Analyst data system (Applied Biosystems, version 1.6.2, the Netherlands). Concentrations in experimental samples were calculated based on the calibration curve in the corresponding matrix.

Hypothalamic transcriptomics (microarray)

Total RNA from the hypothalamus was isolated by using RNeasy Lipid tissue kit (Qiagen, Venlo, The Netherlands). RNA concentrations were measured by absorbance at 260 nm (Nanodrop). RNA quality was checked using the RNA 6000 Nano assay on the Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer (Agilent Technologies, Amsterdam, The Netherlands) according to the manufacturer's protocol. For each mouse, total RNA (100 ng) was labelled using the Ambion WT expression kit (Life Technologies, Bleiswijk, The Netherlands). Micro-array experiments were performed by using Affymetrix Mouse Gene 1.1 ST arrays. In the TNF α treated group, 1 sample gave multiple spots on the array and was therefore excluded from analysis. Array data were analysed using an in-house, on-line system [56]. Briefly, probesets were redefined according to Dai et al. [57] using remapped CDF version 18.0.1 based on the Entrez Gene database. In total these arrays target 21,266 unique genes. Robust multi-array (RMA) analysis was used to obtain expression values [58, 59]. We only took genes into account that had an intensity >20 on

at least 3 arrays and at least 7 probes per genes. Genes were considered differentially expressed at $P < 0.05$ after intensity-based moderated t-statistics [60]. Further functional interpretation of the data was performed through the use of IPA (Ingenuity® Systems, www.ingenuity.com). Genes from the data set that met the cut-off of 1.2 fold change and P value cut-off of 0.05 were considered for the analysis. Upstream regulators were identified by using cut-off values of z-score >1.96 and z-score <-1.96 combined with $P < 0.05$. Furthermore for this upstream regulators analysis, only endogenous metabolites were considered (chemical drugs and compounds were excluded from analysis). Array data have been submitted to the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO), accession number GSE69151.

Plasma cytokines and gut hormones

Plasma levels of TNF- α , amylin (Active), C-Peptide 2, ghrelin (Active), GIP (Total), GLP-1 (Active), glucagon, IL-6, insulin, leptin, MCP-1, Pancreatic Peptide (PP), PYY and resistin were measured using the 12-plex Mouse Metabolic Hormone Magnetic bead panel (Merck Millipore, Amsterdam, The Netherlands). Serum amyloid was measured in liver homogenates using SAA mouse ELISA kit (Life technologies, Bleiswijk, The Netherlands).

Statistics

Data were analysed by statistical analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by a post hoc Bonferroni test or by a Dunnett test. Differences were considered significant at a two-tailed $P < 0.05$. Statistical analyses were performed using Graphpad Prism 5.

Additional file

Additional file 1: Figure S1. Plasma levels of gut hormones. Effect of ipinjection with TNF α , IL-6 or both on A) Resistin, B) Peptide YY, C) Glucagon-like peptide (GLP-1), D) MCP-1, E) Insulin, F) C-peptide, G) Gastric inhibitoryprotein (GIP), H) Amylin, I) Leptin.

Abbreviations

5HIAA: 5-hydroxyindoleacetic acid; 5HT: 5-hydroxytryptamine (serotonin); AgRP: agouti related protein; BBB: blood brain barrier; IDO: indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase (IDO); IL-6: interleukin-6; NPY: neuropeptide Y; POMC: proopiomelanocortin; TNF α : tumor necrosis factor alpha.

Authors' contributions

JD, ML and KN have designed, conducted, analysed and interpreted in vivo animal and in vitro studies. MH has measured and analysed murine hypothalamic metabolites. MB and RW were involved in micro-array analysis of mouse hypothalamus and interpretation of all results. The manuscript contains original unpublished work and is currently not under consideration elsewhere. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Availability of supporting data

Array data have been submitted to the Gene Expression Omnibus, Accession Number GSE69151.

Competing interests

JD, RW, MB, ML, and MH have nothing to disclose. KN is a guest employee at Nutricia Research, a medical nutrition company.

Ethical approval animal experiments

All animal experimental procedures were ethically approved in accordance with the European Community guidelines for the use of laboratory animals and complied with the principles of good laboratory animal care by the Dutch DEC committee reference number 2014038.

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References

- Hopkins SJ, Rothwell NJ. Cytokines and the nervous system. I: expression and recognition. *Trends Neurosci*. 1995;18(2):83–8.
- Zhu CB, Lindler KM, Owens AW, Daws LC, Blakely RD, Hewlett WA. Interleukin-1 receptor activation by systemic lipopolysaccharide induces behavioral despair linked to MAPK regulation of CNS serotonin transporters. *Neuropsychopharmacology*. 2010;35(13):2510–20.
- Endo M, Masaki T, Seike M, Yoshimatsu H. Involvement of stomach ghrelin and hypothalamic neuropeptides in tumor necrosis factor- α -induced hypophagia in mice. *Regul Pept*. 2007;140(1–2):94–100.
- Jang PG, Namkoong C, Kang GM, Hur MW, Kim SW, Kim GH, Kang Y, Jeon MJ, Kim EH, Lee MS, Karin M, Baik JH, Park JY, Lee KU, Kim YB, Kim MS. NF- κ B activation in hypothalamic pro-opiomelanocortin neurons is essential in illness- and leptin-induced anorexia. *J Biol Chem*. 2010;285(13):9706–15.
- Gutierrez EG, Banks WA, Kastin AJ. Murine tumor necrosis factor alpha is transported from blood to brain in the mouse. *J Neuroimmunol*. 1993;47(2):169–76.
- Banks WA, Kastin AJ, Gutierrez EG. Penetration of interleukin-6 across the murine blood-brain barrier. *Neurosci Lett*. 1994;179(1–2):53–6.
- Banks WA, Kastin AJ. Blood to brain transport of interleukin links the immune and central nervous systems. *Life Sci*. 1991;48(25):PL117–21.
- Herman AP, Krawczynska A, Bochenek J, Antushevich H, Herman A, Tomaszewska-Zaremba D. Peripheral injection of SB203580 inhibits the inflammatory-dependent synthesis of proinflammatory cytokines in the hypothalamus. *Biomed Res Int*. 2014;2014:475152.
- Peruzzo B, Pastor FE, Blazquez JL, Schobitz K, Pelaez B, Amat P, Rodriguez EM. A second look at the barriers of the medial basal hypothalamus. *Exp Brain Res*. 2000;132(1):10–26.
- Krisch B, Leonhardt H. The functional and structural border of the neurohemal region of the median eminence. *Cell Tissue Res*. 1978;192(2):327–39.
- Rana I, Stebbing M, Kompa A, Kelly DJ, Krum H, Badoer E. Microglia activation in the hypothalamic PVN following myocardial infarction. *Brain Res*. 2010;1326:96–104.
- Ronaldson PT, Bendayan R. HIV-1 viral envelope glycoprotein gp120 triggers an inflammatory response in cultured rat astrocytes and regulates the functional expression of P-glycoprotein. *Mol Pharmacol*. 2006;70(3):1087–98.

13. Dwarkasing JT, Boeschoten MV, Argilès JM, van Dijk M, Busquets S, Penna F, Toledo M, Laviano A, Witkamp RF, van Norren K. Differences in food intake of tumour-bearing cachectic mice are associated with hypothalamic serotonin signalling. *J Cachexia Sarcopenia Muscle*. 2015;6(1):84–94.
14. Laviano A, Inui A, Meguid MM, Molfino A, Conte C, Rossi Fanelli F. NPY and brain monoamines in the pathogenesis of cancer anorexia. *Nutrition*. 2008;24(9):802–5.
15. Meguid MM, Ramos EJ, Laviano A, Varma M, Sato T, Chen C, Qi Y, Das UN. Tumor anorexia: effects on neuropeptide Y and monoamines in paraventricular nucleus. *Peptides*. 2004;25(2):261–6.
16. Delorme ML, Denis J, Nordlinger B, Boschat M, Opolon P. Relationship between plasma and brain tryptophan in pigs during experimental hepatic coma before and after hemodialysis with selective membranes. *J Neurochem*. 1981;36(3):1058–66.
17. Dawson R, Oparil S. Genetic and salt-related alterations in monoamine neurotransmitters in Dahl salt-sensitive and salt-resistant rats. *Pharmacology*. 1986;33(6):322–33.
18. Calapai G, Corica F, Corsonello A, Sautebin L, Di Rosa M, Campo GM, Buemi M, Mauro VN, Caputi AP. Leptin increases serotonin turnover by inhibition of brain nitric oxide synthesis. *J Clin Invest*. 1999;104(7):975–82.
19. Brunetti L, Orlando G, Recinella L, Leone S, Ferrante C, Chiavaroli A, Lazzarin F, Vacca M. Glucagon-like peptide 1 (7–36) amide (GLP-1) and extendin-4 stimulate serotonin release in rat hypothalamus. *Peptides*. 2008;29(8):1377–81.
20. Nonogaki K, Ohashi-Nozue K, Oka Y. A negative feedback system between brain serotonin systems and plasma active ghrelin levels in mice. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun*. 2006;341(3):703–7.
21. Xu Y, Jones JE, Kohno D, Williams KW, Lee CE, Choi MJ, Anderson JG, Heisler LK, Zigman JM, Lowell BB, Elmquist JK. 5-HT₂CRs expressed by pro-opiomelanocortin neurons regulate energy homeostasis. *Neuron*. 2008;60(4):582–9.
22. Dryden S, Frankish HM, Wang Q, Williams G. Increased feeding and neuropeptide Y (NPY) but not NPY mRNA levels in the hypothalamus of the rat following central administration of the serotonin synthesis inhibitor p-chlorophenylalanine. *Brain Res*. 1996;724(2):232–7.
23. Cangiano C, Laviano A, Meguid MM, Mulieri M, Conversano L, Preziosa I, Rossi-Fanelli F. Effects of administration of oral branched-chain amino acids on anorexia and caloric intake in cancer patients. *J Natl Cancer Inst*. 1996;88(8):550–2.
24. Dwarkasing JT, van Dijk M, Dijk FJ, Boeschoten MV, Faber J, Argiles JM, Laviano A, Muller M, Witkamp RF, van Norren K. Hypothalamic food intake regulation in a cancer-cachectic mouse model. *J Cachexia Sarcopenia Muscle*. 2013;5(2):159–69.
25. Matsumoto M, Togashi H, Yoshioka M, Hirokami M, Tochihara M, Ikeda T, Smith CB, Saito H. Inhibitory effects of clonidine on serotonergic neuronal activity as measured by cerebrospinal fluid serotonin and its metabolite in anesthetized rats. *Life Sci*. 1993;53(8):615–20.
26. Shannon NJ, Gunnet JW, Moore KE. A comparison of biochemical indices of 5-hydroxytryptaminergic neuronal activity following electrical stimulation of the dorsal raphe nucleus. *J Neurochem*. 1986;47(3):958–65.
27. Winberg S, Myrberg AA Jr, Nilsson GE. Predator exposure alters brain serotonin metabolism in bicolor damselfish. *NeuroReport*. 1993;4(4):399–402.
28. Virkkunen M, Linnoila M. Brain serotonin, type II alcoholism and impulsive violence. *J Stud Alcohol Suppl*. 1993;11:163–9.
29. Dhillon SS, Belsham DD. Leptin differentially regulates NPY secretion in hypothalamic cell lines through distinct intracellular signal transduction pathways. *Regul Pept*. 2011;167(2–3):192–200.
30. Dhillon SS, Belsham DD. Estrogen inhibits NPY secretion through membrane-associated estrogen receptor (ER)-alpha in clonal, immortalized hypothalamic neurons. *Int J Obes (Lond)*. 2011;35(2):198–207.
31. Arendt BK, Velazquez-Dones A, Tschumper RC, Howell KG, Ansell SM, Witzig TE, Jelinek DF. Interleukin 6 induces monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 expression in myeloma cells. *Leukemia*. 2002;16(10):2142–7.
32. Kalin S, Heppner FL, Bechmann I, Prinz M, Tschop MH, Yi CX. Hypothalamic innate immune reaction in obesity. *Nat Rev Endocrinol*. 2015;11:339–51.
33. Thaler JP, Yi CX, Schur EA, Guyenet SJ, Hwang BH, Dietrich MO, Zhao X, Sarruf DA, Izgur V, Maravilla KR, Nguyen HT, Fischer JD, Matsen ME, Wise BE, Morton GJ, Horvath TL, Baskin DG, Tschop MH, Schwartz MW. Obesity is associated with hypothalamic injury in rodents and humans. *J Clin Invest*. 2012;122(1):153–62.
34. Acarin L, Gonzalez B, Castellano B. Neuronal, astroglial and microglial cytokine expression after an excitotoxic lesion in the immature rat brain. *Eur J Neurosci*. 2000;12(10):3505–20.
35. Shibata M. Hypothalamic neuronal responses to cytokines. *Yale J Biol Med*. 1990;63(2):147–56.
36. Meeusen R, De Meirleir K. Exercise and brain neurotransmission. *Sports Med*. 1995;20(3):160–88.
37. Meeusen R, Thorre K, Chaouloff F, Sarre S, De Meirleir K, Ebinger G, Michotte Y. Effects of tryptophan and/or acute running on extracellular 5-HT and 5-HIAA levels in the hippocampus of food-deprived rats. *Brain Res*. 1996;740(1–2):245–52.
38. Blomstrand E, Perrett D, Parry-Billings M, Newsholme EA. Effect of sustained exercise on plasma amino acid concentrations and on 5-hydroxytryptamine metabolism in six different brain regions in the rat. *Acta Physiol Scand*. 1989;136(3):473–81.
39. Chaouloff F, Laude D, Elghozi JL. Physical exercise: evidence for differential consequences of tryptophan on 5-HT synthesis and metabolism in central serotonergic cell bodies and terminals. *J Neural Transm*. 1989;78(2):121–30.
40. Barton DA, Esler MD, Dawood T, Lambert EA, Haikermal D, Brenchley C, Socratous F, Hastings J, Guo L, Wiesner G, Kaye DM, Bayles R, Schlaich MP, Lambert GW. Elevated brain serotonin turnover in patients with depression: effect of genotype and therapy. *Arch Gen Psychiatry*. 2008;65(1):38–46.
41. Vermeiren Y, Van Dam D, Aerts T, Engelborghs S, De Deyn PP. Monoaminergic neurotransmitter alterations in postmortem brain regions of depressed and aggressive patients with Alzheimer's disease. *Neurobiol Aging*. 2014;35(12):2691–700.
42. Vermeiren Y, Van Dam D, Aerts T, Engelborghs S, De Deyn PP. Brain region-specific monoaminergic correlates of neuropsychiatric symptoms in Alzheimer's disease. *J Alzheimers Dis*. 2014;41(3):819–33.
43. Dinel AL, Andre C, Aubert A, Ferreira G, Laye S, Castanon N. Lipopolysaccharide-induced brain activation of the indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase and depressive-like behavior are impaired in a mouse model of metabolic syndrome. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*. 2014;40:48–59.
44. Sato T, Laviano A, Meguid MM, Chen C, Rossi-Fanelli F, Hatakeyama K. Involvement of plasma leptin, insulin and free tryptophan in cytokine-induced anorexia. *Clin Nutr*. 2003;22(2):139–46.
45. Dunn AJ. Stress-related changes in cerebral catecholamine and indoleamine metabolism: lack of effect of adrenalectomy and corticosterone. *J Neurochem*. 1988;51(2):406–12.
46. Xiang B, Zhang G, Guo L, Li XA, Morris AJ, Daugherty A, Whiteheart SW, Smyth SS, Li Z. Platelets protect from septic shock by inhibiting macrophage-dependent inflammation via the cyclooxygenase 1 signaling pathway. *Nat Commun*. 2013;4:2657.
47. Kim YW, Kim KH, Ahn DK, Kim HS, Kim JY, Lee DC, Park SY. Time-course changes of hormones and cytokines by lipopolysaccharide and its relation with anorexia. *J Physiol Sci*. 2007;57(3):159–65.
48. Kakizaki Y, Watanobe H, Kohsaka A, Suda T. Temporal profiles of interleukin-1 beta, interleukin-6, and tumor necrosis factor-alpha in the plasma and hypothalamic paraventricular nucleus after intravenous or intraperitoneal administration of lipopolysaccharide in the rat: estimation by push-pull perfusion. *Endocr J*. 1999;46(4):487–96.
49. Schobitz B, Pezeshki G, Pohl T, Hemmann U, Heinrich PC, Holsboer F, Reul JM. Soluble interleukin-6 (IL-6) receptor augments central effects of IL-6 in vivo. *FASEB J*. 1995;9(8):659–64.
50. Wang J, Leibowitz KL. Central insulin inhibits hypothalamic galanin and neuropeptide Y gene expression and peptide release in intact rats. *Brain Res*. 1997;777(1–2):231–6.
51. Amaral ME, Barbuio R, Milanski M, Romanatto T, Barbosa HC, Nadruz W, Bertolo MB, Boschero AC, Saad MJ, Franchini KG, Velloso LA. Tumor necrosis factor-alpha activates signal transduction in hypothalamus and modulates the expression of pro-inflammatory proteins and orexigenic/anorexigenic neurotransmitters. *J Neurochem*. 2006;98(1):203–12.
52. Arruda AP, Milanski M, Romanatto T, Solon C, Coope A, Alberici LC, Festuccia WT, Hirabara SM, Ropelle E, Curi R, Carvalheira JB, Vercesi AE, Velloso LA. Hypothalamic actions of tumor necrosis factor alpha provide the

- thermogenic core for the wastage syndrome in cachexia. *Endocrinology*. 2010;151(2):683–94.
53. Senaris RM, Trujillo ML, Navia B, Comes G, Ferrer B, Giralto M, Hidalgo J. Interleukin-6 regulates the expression of hypothalamic neuropeptides involved in body weight in a gender-dependent way. *J Neuroendocrinol*. 2011;23(8):675–86.
 54. Shinozaki T, Kimura M, Hosoyamada M, Shibasaki T. Fluvoxamine inhibits weight gain and food intake in food restricted hyperphagic Wistar rats. *Biol Pharm Bull*. 2008;31(12):2250–4.
 55. Dryden S, Frankish HM, Wang Q, Pickavance L, Williams G. The serotonergic agent fluoxetine reduces neuropeptide Y levels and neuropeptide Y secretion in the hypothalamus of lean and obese rats. *Neuroscience*. 1996;72(2):557–66.
 56. Lin K, Kools H, de Groot PJ, Gavai AK, Basnet RK, Cheng F, Wu J, Wang X, Lommen A, Hooiveld GJ, Bonnema G, Visser RG, Muller MR, Leunissen JA. MADMAX—management and analysis database for multiple omics experiments. *J Integr Bioinform*. 2011;8(2):160.
 57. Dai M, Wang P, Boyd AD, Kostov G, Atthey B, Jones EG, Bunney WE, Myers RM, Speed TP, Akil H, Watson SJ, Meng F. Evolving gene/transcript definitions significantly alter the interpretation of GeneChip data. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2005;33(20):e175.
 58. Irizarry RA, Bolstad BM, Collin F, Cope LM, Hobbs B, Speed TP. Summaries of Affymetrix GeneChip probe level data. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2003;31(4):e15.
 59. Bolstad BM, Irizarry RA, Astrand M, Speed TP. A comparison of normalization methods for high density oligonucleotide array data based on variance and bias. *Bioinformatics*. 2003;19(2):185–93.
 60. Sartor MA, Tomlinson CR, Wesselkamper SC, Sivaganesan S, Leikauf GD, Medvedovic M. Intensity-based hierarchical Bayes method improves testing for differentially expressed genes in microarray experiments. *BMC Bioinformatics*. 2006;7:538.